

Using Data Mining Techniques to explore Shopping Addiction and Emotion Based Decision Making in Consumers

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Abstract

Compulsive shopping and spending is described as a pattern of chronic, repetitive purchasing that becomes difficult to stop and ultimately results in harmful consequences. It is defined as an impulse control disorder and has features similar to other addictive disorders without involving the use of an intoxicating drug. There has been described as Compulsive buying disorder which occurs when obsessive buying — basically a shopping addiction — leads to negative consequences. The condition affects nearly six percent of the population of the United States. In addition to the distress that arises from the disorder itself, compulsive buying disorder is also strongly indicative of a co morbid condition. Through this paper, shopping addiction is combined with emotion based decision making in order to study emotional empathy and generally consumer behavior of social media users. Emotion-based decision-making, the ability to use emotions when making decisions is a prerequisite for sound judgment in human beings. Emotional empathy is a capacity which allows an appreciation of separateness of human beings and at the same time allows them to connect by attending to and feeling the emotional experiences of others (Hanson, R., (2007). Emotional empathy builds on one's tendency of emotional awareness. Individuals who make compulsive shopping maybe lack in emotional empathy and the decision making is more emotional rather than rational.

The data were collected by completion of the self-report questionnaires "Bergen Shopping Addiction Scale" the "Emotion-Based Decision-Making Scale", "Balanced Emotional Empathy Scale" and used for the application of data mining methods. Specifically, for the collection of data electronic versions of the above scales were created through Google Forms service and posted through the website "<http://www.cicos.gr/iccmi2017/saeb>". Then the collected data were selected for analysis, with relevant transformations in order to have a suitable form for the implementation of the respective machine learning algorithms included in the software package R. The results of the present study represent among others, that the emotion based decision making in combination with low levels of emotional empathy can be important predictive factor for the shopping addiction behavior.

Keywords: Shopping Addiction, Decision-Making, Emotional Empathy, Consumers, Social Networks, R, Data Mining

1. INTRODUCTION

Shopping can be an important source of self-expression, self-definition or therapy. However, if it becomes uncontrolled or excessive, it becomes problematic. Compulsive buying is an uncontrollable urge that repeatedly compels a person to buy in order to bring temporary relief from psychological distress arising from bad mood, if everyday circumstances of life are deserted. As a result, compulsive shoppers buy items that they do not need and cannot afford. Afterwards, usually they feel guilty about their decision about succumbing to their urges. Not a few times that they have undergone financial damage for which their decisions are responsible.

Current research has focused on the causes of compulsive buying and particularly on the factors that contribute to its etiology. There are few studies that have dealt with the cognitive processes that lead a consumer to be an compulsive buyer. Decision-making and especially emotion-focused strategies are a process that can provide efficient framework for the explanation of compulsive behavior that leads on shopping addiction.

1.1. Decision-making

Decision-making is a field of interest for philosophers, economists, psychologists, and neuroscientists, among others. A fundamental question that drives research in this area is why do people who are presented with the same options make different choices? What is it about the cognitive and neurological processes that lead people to different outcomes? Why do rational models such as those used in economics and the classical decision-making theory not always accurately predict an individual's behavior? These questions and others are particularly true of decision-making under risk, uncertainty, and ambiguity. These questions are addressed by the emerging field of neuroeconomics which is the combination of the different perspectives and theories of psychology, economics, and neuroscience.

Image10: Pyramid outline

1.2. The role of emotion in decision-making

Until recently, decision researchers have not focused on the role of emotion as a separate factor in the decision process. Emotion was viewed only as a negative influence and hindrance to the rational decision process. More recently, some researchers have stressed the importance of environmental, social, and emotional influences on decision-making.

There has been a continuous debate over the independence of cognition and emotion, and the conflict between rational and emotional reasoning. Current theories suggest there are two dominant systems people use to understand and assess risk: the “analytic system” and the “experiential system.” The “analytic system” involves conscious and deliberate cognitive processes that employ various algorithms and normative rules to produce logical, reason-oriented, behavior. In contrast, the “experiential system” uses past experiences, emotion-related associations, and intuitions when making decisions. The experiential system relies more on unconscious rather than conscious processes. Most models of decision-making assume the process to be rational, which would exclude the possibility of emotion playing a role, other than of a hindrance. The truth is that the two systems emotional and rational decision-making must work in collaboration in order for the decision-maker to reach a rational decision.

1.3. Emotion-Based strategies in Consumers

Emotion is a key element of judgment and decision-making, as they bring important information about who we are and how we interact with others. Little is known about how emotions affect performance in marketing. Applying emotional theories to marketing has led to research centered on: 1) Emotion as a precursor to behavior, 2) Emotion as a consequence, and 3) Emotion as mediated or moderate influence on marketing relationships. What is the role of emotions in exchanges and relationships and how do consumers use emotional information to make marketing decisions?

Emotion-based decision-making, the ability to use emotions when making decisions is a prerequisite for sound judgment in human beings. Emotional empathy is a capacity which allows an appreciation of separateness of human beings and at the same time allows them to connect by attending to and feeling the emotional experiences of others

Empathy is the ability to understand the emotions, thoughts, behaviors, and actions of others and respond appropriately in order to assist someone in need. Empathy is also seen as a measure of an individual's other-oriented thinking and responsiveness over self-oriented responses. It is widely agreed that empathy is a multifaceted construct with two dimensions: cognitive empathy and emotional empathy. One distinction between the two dimensions is that emotional empathy relates to the emotional arousal one experiences when they see or identify with someone else's misfortunes, while cognitive empathy pertains to the mental understanding of someone else's misfortune without having experienced it before. Emotional empathy builds on one's tendency of emotional awareness. Individuals who make compulsive shopping maybe lack in emotional empathy and the decision making is more emotional rather than rational.

1.4. Bergen Shopping Addiction Scale (BSAS)

The Bergen Shopping Addiction Scale (BSAS) is a brief screening psychometric tool for assessing the severity of shopping addiction. It consists of 28 statements. The participant is asked to rate how strongly each of the statements relates to their thoughts and behavior in the last 12 months. Each item is rated on a 5 point continuum of agreement: completely disagree, disagree, neither disagree, nor agree, agree, completely agree. Groups of 4 items are targeted toward each of 7 addiction criteria (salience, mood modification, conflict, tolerance, withdrawal, relapse, and problems). Higher scores indicate higher levels of shopping addiction.

1.5. Emotion-Based Decision-Making Scale (EBDMS)

The Emotion-Based Decision-Making Scale (EBDMS) attempts to measure a person's tendency to rely upon emotions and "gut reactions" in making decisions. It has 10 items that use a 5-point Likert response scale. Five items are reverse-coded.

1.6. The Balanced Emotional Empathy Scale (BEES)

The Balanced Emotional Empathy Scale (BEES) is designed to assess the emotive component of empathy. Typically, the empathy construct has been separated into two types: cognitive and emotional. Cognitive empathy refers to imaginatively understanding another person's thoughts, feelings and actions. Emotional empathy is feeling the emotion of another person, but maintaining a compassionate, other-focused perspective. The above questionnaire provides an indication of five components of emotional intelligence.

Self-awareness: This component provides the basis for all the other components of emotional intelligence. Self-awareness means being aware of what you are feeling, being conscious of the emotions within yourself.

Managing emotions: The second key component of emotional intelligence is managing emotions. This means you are able to balance your moods so that worry, anxiety, fear, or anger does not get in the way of what needs to be done. People who manage their emotions perform better because they are able to think clearly.

Motivating oneself: This ability to be hopeful and optimistic despite obstacles, setbacks, or even outright failure is crucial for pursuing long-term goals in life or in business.

Empathy: The fourth component is empathy, which means being able to put yourself in someone else's shoes—to recognize what others are feeling without them needing to tell you.

Social skill: The ability to connect to others, build positive relationships, respond to the emotions of others and influence others is the final component of emotional intelligence.

Image 11

2. METHODOLOGY

In this paper were applied Machine Learning and Data Mining methods in order to evaluate the Bergen Shopping Addiction Scale (BSAS), the Emotion-Based Decision-Making Scale (EMDMS), the Balanced Emotional Empathy Scale (BEES) of social network consumers. The methodology, that was adopted, consists of three concrete phases. During the first phase electronic questionnaires were created and posted through the website “<http://www.cicos.gr/iccmi2017/saeb>”. Subsequently, data were collected and preprocessed from the questionnaires. The data set for analysis was consisted of demographics elements of responders, such as the gender, the birth-place, the place of present residence, educational background of both the respondents and their parents, professional occupation of parents and also of subscales of the BSAS, EMDMS, and BEES tests. During the third phase, the data set was analyzed based on Data Mining techniques and evaluate the results. More specifically, we utilized classification algorithms so as to manage to describe the hidden patterns underlying in the data. Decision trees are a powerful way in order to represent and facilitate statements analysis (psychological) principally, comprising successive decisions and variable results in a designated period.

2.1. Shopping Addiction, Emotion-focused Decision Making, Emotional Empathy

Shopping addiction is a chronic, repetitive purchasing behavior that becomes a primary response to negative events and feelings. It includes classical symptoms of addiction equivalent to craving and withdrawal. A key feature distinguishing shopping addiction from normal consumption is the focus on the buying process itself, rather than the items bought. Items bought during shopping addiction episodes are usually used less than expected, hidden, or thrown away. Recent studies showed that up to 5% of adult Americans have shopping addiction. This behavioral addiction results in adverse consequences, including financial and legal problems, psychological distress (depression, guilt), and interpersonal conflict. The behavior is focused on the act of buying itself, which provides a short-term sense of pleasure or relief from negative mood and continues even if individuals repeatedly experience negative consequences, such as marked distress, social problems, financial bankruptcy, or delinquency.

On a cognitive level, *impaired decision-making* abilities (emotion-focused rather than rational) have been pointed out as potential etiological factor, because people suffering from pathological buying, decide to engage in buying which is immediate rewarding, but implies negative long-term consequences.

Emotional empathy plays an important role in social communication and reflects how we share basic emotions, like happiness, sadness, anger, and fear. The ability to recognize and empathize with others is necessary for fostering and maintaining relationships, including romantic relationships. The value of emotional empathy in social relationships can perhaps best be evidenced in circumstances when there is an empathic imbalance such as shopping addiction. For example, a lack of emotional empathy in shopping maybe is associated with low cognitive flexibility, self-awareness and emotion management.

Overall, shopping addiction behavior maybe explained by the use of emotion-focused strategies in decision-making and also emotional empathy maybe contribute as a mediating factor in the impulsivity of shopping behavior.

2.2. Data Mining Techniques

Data Mining is an emerging knowledge discovery process of extracting previously unknown, actionable information from very large scientific and commercial databases. It is imposed by the explosive growth of such databases. Usually, a data mining process extracts rules by processing high dimensional categorical and/or numerical data. Classification, clustering and association are the most well known data mining tasks. Classification is one of the most popular data mining tasks. Classification aims at extracting knowledge which can be used to classify data into predefined classes, described by a set of attributes. The extracted knowledge can be represented using various schemas.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Association Rule Learning

Association rule learning is a rule-based machine learning method for discovering interesting relations between variables in large databases. It is intended to identify strong rules discovered in databases using some measures of interestingness. They are usually required to satisfy a user-specified minimum support and a user-specified minimum confidence at the same time. Association rule generation is usually split up into two separate steps:

- iv. A minimum support threshold is applied to find all frequent itemsets in a database.
- v. A minimum confidence constraint is applied to these frequent itemsets in order to form rules.
- vi. While the second step is straightforward, the first step needs more attention.

Three most widely used measures ³for selecting interesting rules are:

Support

Support is an indication of how frequently the itemset appears in the dataset.

Confidence

Confidence is an indication of how often the rule has been found to be true.

Lift

Is the ratio of the observed support to that expected if X and Y were independent.

Apriori is an algorithm for frequent item set mining and association rule learning over transactional databases. It proceeds by identifying the frequent individual items in the database and extending them to larger and larger item sets as long as those item sets appear sufficiently often in the database. The frequent item sets determined by Apriori can be used to determine association rules which highlight general trends in the database.

Visualizing Extracted Rules

Visualization has a long history of making large data sets better accessible using techniques like selecting and zooming. In this paper we use the R-extension package “arulesViz” which implements several known and novel visualization techniques to explore association rules. Below, we represent the extracted rules in a variety of ways with different techniques.

Graph-based visualization

Graph-based visualization offers a very clear representation of rules but they tend to easily become cluttered and thus are only viable for very small sets of rules

³Every rule is composed by two different sets of items, also known as itemsets, X and Y, where X is called antecedent or left-hand-side (LHS) and Y consequent or right-hand-side (RHS).

Grouped Matrix Visualization

Antecedents (columns) in the matrix are grouped using clustering. Groups are represented as balloons in the matrix.

Parallel coordinates visualization

Parallel coordinates plots are designed to visualize multidimensional data where each dimension is displayed separately on the x-axis and the y-axis is shared. Each data point is represented by a line connecting the values for each dimension

Figure 10

Figure 11

Parallel coordinates plot for 24 rules

Figure 12

Apriori rules

Specifically of our use we altered the Support and Confidence values to 50% and 90% respectively

A sample of the extracted rules (Top 8)

lhsrhs	support	confidence	lift
2 {BSAS_Conflict=HIGH}	=> {BSAS_overall=HIGH}	0.3448276	1.0000000 1.611111
18 {BSAS_Relapse=HIGH}	=> {BSAS_overall=HIGH}	0.5172414	1.0000000 1.611111
25 {BSAS_Tolerance=HIGH,BSAS_Problems=HIGH}	=> {BSAS_overall=HIGH}	0.3448276	1.0000000 1.611111
30 {BSAS_Tolerance=HIGH,BEES_managing.emotions=LOW}	=> {BSAS_overall=HIGH}	0.3103448	1.0000000 1.611111
129 {BSAS_Problems=HIGH,EBDSMS_logic=LOW}	=> {BSAS_overall=HIGH}	0.3103448	1.0000000 1.611111
17 {BSAS_Problems=HIGH}	=> {BSAS_overall=HIGH}	0.4827586	0.9333333 1.503704
16 {BSAS_Salience=HIGH}	=> {BSAS_overall=HIGH}	0.4482759	0.9285714 1.496032
147 {BSAS_Withdrawal=HIGH,BEES_managing.emotions=LOW}	=> {BSAS_overall=HIGH}	0.3103448	0.9000000 1.450000

The full spectrum of the exported rules (24) after data mining analysis of the results are analyzed below: Females (age range: 19-22) have shown high scores in the factors of conflict tolerance and problems rather than males of the same age range. Both males and females of every age indicate low rates in almost all the factors of EBDMS. Also, both male and female (age range: above 20 years) present high rates in the factors of BSAS.

3.2. Correlation Analysis

Correlation is any of a broad class of statistical relationships involving dependence, though in common usage it most often refers to the extent to which two variables have a linear relationship with each other.

Figure 13

As it is shown above, there is high negative correlation between BSAS and BEES questionnaires and some low positive correlation between BSAS and the emotion factor of the EBDMS questionnaire.

If the measures of correlation used are product-moment coefficients, the correlation matrix is the same as the covariance matrix of the standardized random variables $X_i / \sigma(X_i)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

4. CONCLUSION

To conclude, emotion-focused decision making in combination with emotional empathy can contribute effectively in shopping addiction behavior and can provide a broader framework of investigations of the process of such behaviors. The emerged field of neuroeconomics with the combination of different perspectives and theories of psychology, economics, neuroscience and informatics can explain in a more comprehensive manner the crucial role of cognition and emotions in shopping behavior generally and its impulse features that characterize shopping addiction.

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